

Edible plates from wheat bran and blackcurrant pomace: A multidisciplinary approach to by-product valorization

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Eleven edible plate (EP) formulations with different additives were developed.
- EPs contained tocopherols, tocotrienols, alkylresorcinols, anthocyanins, and fiber.
- Gluten/xanthan and lactic acid improved strength, reduced water and oil absorption.
- EPs were safe and sensorially acceptable, with 5-HMF levels within safe limits.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

This study developed biodegradable, edible plates (EP; plural EPs) using wheat bran (WB 67–90%) and blackcurrant pomace (BP 3–10%) as sustainable plastic alternatives. Eleven formulations were tested with additives: stabilizers (chitosan, levan, xanthan), plasticizers (glycerol, lactic acid), crosslinking agents (citric acid, lecithin), and film-forming agents (gluten, gelatin). EPs with WB (67–80%) and BP (4–5%), plus gluten or xanthan and lactic acid, showed high fracture strength (148.7–235.2 N) and low water/oil absorption. SEM showed dense, compact structures; in contrast, >8% BP and 10% apple puree were associated with a less uniform, more defect-prone structure with visible void-like regions. All EPs had safe levels of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural. Functional compounds were present, including tocopherols, tocotrienols, alkylresorcinols, anthocyanins, and fiber. Sensory analysis highlighted EPs 21.2 and 25.1 as the most favorable in structure, taste, and visual appeal. These findings show that combining food by-products with targeted bio-additives can yield sustainable, nutritious, and consumer-acceptable EPs, supporting win-win-win environmental, nutritional, and industrial sustainability goals.

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1. Introduction

Single-use packaging materials, such as plastic, polystyrene, and paper, have long been used for disposable tableware (DT) due to their low cost and convenience (Chen et al., 2021). However, growing environmental concerns have led to regulatory changes, particularly in the European Union, where many single-use plastics were officially banned under the Single-Use Plastics Directive in 2019 (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2019). While this legislation has significantly reduced plastic usage in EU member states, similar materials are still widely used in countries such as the United States, China, India, and Russia (Barone et al., 2025; Chen et al., 2021; Sarisaltuk and Gulden, 2025). In response to plastic bans, there has been a noticeable shift toward paper-based alternatives as more sustainable options for DT (Simantiris, 2024). Although paper is biodegradable, its application in food service is limited due to its high hydrophilicity and poor barrier properties against water and oil, making it unsuitable for hot or liquid foods (Mekonnen et al., 2013; Shrestha, 2023). To address these limitations, paper packaging is often coated with polymeric substances such as per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), which enhance resistance to moisture and oil. However, PFAS are persistent environmental pollutants that pose significant risks to human health and the environment (Coffin et al., 2023). In addition, single-use paper products have been found to contain other hazardous chemicals, including mutagenic agents and substances classified as carcinogenic, which can leach into products or the environment within minutes of exposure (Simantiris, 2024). Polystyrene, commonly used for lightweight, insulating containers, decomposes extremely slowly, potentially taking hundreds to thousands of years and releasing toxic substances during degradation or incineration (Ali et al., 2025; Hwang et al., 2020). The growing impact of plastic waste on climate change and global efforts to promote a circular economy have intensified the search for sustainable packaging alternatives (Zhu et al., 2022). Edible tableware (ET) produced from plant-based by-products offers a compelling solution, uniting biodegradability with structural functionality and nutritional benefits (Gupta et al., 2023). Furthermore, incorporating food industry by-products into ET supports the “zero-waste” philosophy and holds significant potential to reduce environmental burdens associated with conventional food packaging waste (Dybka-Stepień et al., 2021; Hamed et al., 2022; Vyshali and Muthamma, 2022). Research in this field has primarily focused on creating edible packaging and tableware using various natural ingredients, including cereals such as wheat (Rishi et al., 2024), rice (Matheswari and Arivuchudar, 2024), corn (Pantović et al., 2025), sorghum (Matheswari and Arivuchudar, 2024; Manivel and Paramasivam, 2024), millet (Rajendran et al., 2020); legumes like chickpeas (Matheswari and Arivuchudar, 2024); starches such as potato (Gupta et al., 2023), cassava (Ferreira et al., 2020; Lilavanichakul and Yoksan, 2023), corn (George, 2023); and plant-based fibers like oat fiber (Olt et al., 2020), psyllium husk (Tóth and Halász, 2019), olive pomace (Grzelczyk et al., 2024), flaxseed (Andrejko and Blicharz-Kania, 2024). Recent studies have further demonstrated that biodegradable edible films based on protein-polysaccharide systems can be engineered to provide antibacterial functionality for food preservation, highlighting the growing interest in multifunctional edible packaging materials (Khan et al., 2025; Lv et al., 2024).

To date, no prior studies have demonstrated the feasibility of integrating by-products from different industries, such as wheat bran (WB) from cereal processing and blackcurrant pomace (BP) from wine production, with a range of functional additives, including softening agents, emulsifiers, and structural stabilizers, for the development of ET, specifically EPs. In this study, WB was selected as the primary structural and fiber-rich component due to its high content of dietary fiber and bioactive lipophilic compounds, which contribute to matrix formation, mechanical strength, and nutritional value. In contrast, BP was chosen primarily as a source of antioxidant and functional compounds, especially anthocyanins and phenolic compounds, which can enhance

oxidative stability, color, and sensory appeal. Additionally, apple puree was incorporated as a natural, food-grade plasticizing component to improve matrix flexibility and palatability through its sugars and pectic polysaccharides, consistent with previous applications of fruit purees in edible films and coatings, while their application in ET remains limited (Janowicz et al., 2023; Syarifuddin et al., 2025). This novel combination, particularly the use of wine-derived BP, which has not been previously investigated in this context, has the potential to enhance consumer appeal through improved visual and flavor qualities. Additionally, it may strengthen key physicochemical properties such as fracture resistance and moisture stability. These formulations are also expected to serve as a rich source of bioactive and functional compounds, including anthocyanins from BP (Górnaś et al., 2016; Untea et al., 2024), and free and bound phenolics, tocotrienols, alkylresorcinols, and dietary fiber from WB (Górnaś et al., 2015; Martín-García et al., 2021; Radenkova et al., 2018). These by-products, when combined with bio-based additives such as xanthan and chitosan, polysaccharides valued for their thickening and gelling properties (Chaturvedi et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2015), can be further enhanced with plasticizers and emulsifiers like glycerol, lecithin, and sorbitol, which improve the flexibility and texture of the final product (Farhan and Hani, 2017). Additionally, the incorporation of gluten into ET formulations functions as a film-forming and binding agent (Xu and Li, 2023), while cross-linking agents such as citric acid and lecithin enhance the cohesion and structural integrity of the edible matrix. The use of these ingredients not only addresses the ecological concerns associated with plastic waste but also introduces nutritional and sensory benefits to the ET.

However, while these ET offer numerous nutritional advantages, there is a potential downside associated with the formation of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (5-HMF), especially prominent in high-heat processes. Its presence in food products is a concern due to potential toxicity in large amounts, making it an important aspect to monitor during manufacturing (Martins et al., 2022). While 5-HMF has been observed in various foods like honey and fruit juices (Shapla et al., 2018), its elevated concentrations in processed food and ET must be carefully assessed to ensure consumer safety.

Therefore, the current study focused on the development of biodegradable EPs, from food processing by-products (WB and BP), combined with various functional additives. While the biodegradable nature of the selected plant-based ingredients is well established, the present work primarily emphasizes material formulation and performance, and systematic biodegradation and compostability assessments will be addressed in future studies. Accordingly, this study was designed as a comparative screening of 11 prototype formulations to identify promising compositions within the tested design space, rather than as a formal optimization study. The formulations were designed to exhibit desirable physicochemical properties such as fracture resistance, water and oil barrier capacity, and structural stability, while also providing functional and health-promoting benefits through anthocyanins, tocotrienols, and tocopherols, and ensuring health safety by maintaining controlled levels of 5-HMF.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Raw material, additives and reagents

WB was obtained from the manufacturer of grains “Dobeles dzirnavnieks” (Dobele, Latvia), while BP was obtained from the wine producer “Tērvetes vīni” (Tērvete, Latvia). Apple puree (cultivar ‘Baltais Dzidrais’) was supplied by the Institute of Horticulture (LatHort) (Dobele, Latvia). Glycerol, gluten, xanthan gum from *Xanthomonas campestris*, lactose, lecithin, citric acid, and food-grade gelatin were purchased from “Gemoss” (Rīga, Latvia). 80% Sugar syrup and potato starch were sourced from a local supermarket “Rimi” (Dobele, Latvia). Lactic acid, sorbitol, chitosan ($M_w = 190\text{--}310$ kDa), dextran from *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* ($M_w = 1500\text{--}800$ kDa) obtained from Sigma

Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). The levan with a molecular weight of 15435 kDa was synthesized according to the previous protocol (Radenkovs et al., 2023).

Ethyl acetate, *n*-hexane, ethanol and methanol (HPLC-grade), glycerol, mannitol, arabinose, fructose, glucose, mannose, sucrose, maltose, lactose, potassium hydroxide, sodium chloride, pyrogallol and 5-HMF, were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). The anthocyanin standards (delphinidin-3-*O*-glucoside, delphinidin-3-*O*-rutinoside, cyanidin-3-*O*-glucoside, cyanidin-3-*O*-rutinoside were obtained from Extrasynthèse (Lyon, France). Tocotrienol and tocopherol homologue (α , β , γ , and δ) standards were received from LGC Standards (Teddington, Middlesex, UK) and Merck (Darmstadt, Germany), respectively.

2.2. Preparation of EPs

The WB and BP, due to their different initial moisture contents, were dehydrated separately at 65 ± 1 °C for 48 h using a “B. Master BM40” dryer (Tauro Essiccatori, Vicenza, Italy) to reach a moisture content of 3–5%, as determined gravimetrically according to the method of Ruiz (2005), and were subsequently ground using a “Knifetec 1095” laboratory mill (FOSS, Hoganas, Sweden) to reach particle size ≤ 0.5 mm. The ingredients were mixed thoroughly according to the formulations specified in Table 1 using a “Vevor 2500 g” electric grain grinder (Vevor, Shanghai, China) at a maximum operating speed of 32,000 rpm for 2 min to ensure homogeneous blending, and were subsequently stored in vacuum-sealed polyethylene bags, protected from light and oxygen, for a maximum of 2 day at 21 °C. Before EP formation, the mold was placed in a “Joos LAP-40” hydraulic hot-press (Gottfried Joos Maschinenfabrik, Pfalzgrafenweiler) featuring a piston measuring 1×125 mm, a platen area of 500×500 mm, and an operational pressure of 326 bar. The mold underwent preheating for 15 min at 160 ± 1 °C, after which it was removed and its edges were uniformly coated with rapeseed oil to prevent sticking. A precise amount of 200 g of the prepared formulation was evenly distributed across the mold surface. Subsequently, the mold was repositioned in the hydraulic press, where pressing occurred at 160 ± 1 °C under optimized pressure conditions (Fig. S1).

The forming process followed a multi-stage pressure profile over an 8-min cycle. Initially, a pressure of 4.0 MPa (corresponding to 250 kN applied over a 250×250 mm mold area) was applied for 3 min to ensure material compaction and shaping. This was followed by a reduction to 1.6 MPa for 3 min to promote uniform densification and moisture redistribution. Subsequently, the pressure was lowered to 0.8 MPa for 1

min to stabilize the structure, followed by a gradual release to atmospheric pressure during the final minute of the cycle. The EP was then carefully removed and allowed to cool at room temperature (22 ± 2 °C), numbered, and packaged in a protective bag to prevent moisture absorption. In total, eleven EPs were produced under these optimized conditions.

2.3. Measurement of EP thickness

The thickness of the EPs was determined using a “Fowler Ultra-CAL V 6” electronic caliper (Fowler High Precision, USA). To ensure consistency and representativeness, measurements were taken at three specific locations on each side of the plate: the edge (1), the plate rise (2, slope), and near the center (3, flat base) (Fig. S2). The mean value of these measurements was calculated to obtain the average thickness for each EP. The instrument provides high precision, with an accuracy of 0.02 mm, a resolution of 0.01 mm, a maximum permissible error of 0.02 mm, and a repeatability of 0.01 mm.

2.4. Measurement of EP fracture force

For the measurement of fracture force, EPs were placed on the platform of a “TMS-PRO Texture Analyzing System” (Food Technology Corporation, VA, USA). This system was equipped with a wedge-shaped probe that has a 60° angle, is 25 mm wide, and 1 mm sharp (ref. 130064R). The EPs were positioned to ensure that the force was applied perpendicularly to the surface of the plate using the probe. A load cell was utilized to gradually apply force until fracture occurred. The force required to fracture the EPs was recorded in Newtons (N) at the point of failure. The test was conducted at a speed of 10 mm per minute. Each EP underwent two tests, and the data were analyzed to determine the average fracture force for each EP. Each EP was tested thrice, and the mean value was used for statistical analysis ($n = 3$).

2.5. Measurement of EP color

The color of the EPs was measured using the “Konica Minolta” spectrophotometer CM-2500c (Konica Minolta Sensing Americas, Inc., NY, USA) following the methodology described by Andrejko & Blicharz-Kania (2024). Additionally, chromatic characteristics such as total color difference (ΔE), chroma (C^*), browning index (BI), and hue angle (h°) were calculated according to the methods described by Guerrero et al. (2011) and Nayaka et al. (2022), using Equations (1)–(5).

Table 1
Composition of EPs.

Ingredients, % w/w	EP											
	18.2	28.1	7.2	25.1	21.2	18.2	15.1	16.1	1.2	12.1	14.1	22.2
Wheat bran	80	70	70	70	67	80	80	90	70	80	80	75
Blackcurrant pomace	4	5	5	10	8	10	5	4	5	3	3	5
Apple puree	3	10	10	–	–	–	–	3	–	–	12.8	–
Glycerol	1.8	–	5	2.7	4.5	–	5	1	0.5	0.6	0.6	1.8
Gluten	5	–	5	–	–	5	5	2	5	3	–	2
0.9% NaCl solution	1	1	–	1	2	–	–	–	–	–	–	2
80% Sugar syrup	5	2	–	3	3	–	–	–	–	–	–	5
Xanthan	–	2	–	–	5	–	–	–	–	–	–	5
Lactose	–	–	–	–	5	–	–	–	–	–	–	4
Potato starch	–	–	–	1.2	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Lecithin	–	10	–	3	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Lactic acid	–	–	–	1	–	5	5	–	–	–	–	–
Chitosan	–	–	–	0.2	0.2	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Citric acid	0.2	–	–	0.4	0.9	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.2
Food gelatin	–	–	0.2	0.3	–	–	–	–	1	–	–	–
Levan	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.6	0.3	–	–
Sorbitol	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.5	–	–	–
Dextran	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	0.3	–
Water	–	–	4.8	7.2	4.6	–	–	–	17.4	–	–	–

Note: “–” indicates the ingredient was not used in that formulation.

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{(L_2^* - L_1^*)^2 + (a_2^* - a_1^*)^2 + (b_2^* - b_1^*)^2} \quad (1)$$

where: L^* , a^* , and b^* are the color values in CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ color space;

$$C^* = \sqrt{a^{*2} + b^{*2}} \quad (2)$$

where: C^* is the chroma; a^* and b^* are the color values in CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ color space. The browning index was calculated using the following equation

$$BI = \frac{100(x - 0.31)}{0.17} \quad (3)$$

where: in Equation 3 (x)

$$x = \frac{(a^* + 1.75L)}{5.645L^* + a^* - 3,012b^*} \quad (4)$$

$$(h^\circ) = \arctan \frac{b^*}{a^*} \quad (5)$$

2.6. Sample preparation and HPLC-RID analysis of sugar and sugar alcohol content in EPs

Prior to carbohydrate extraction, the EP samples were ground into a fine powder using a ball mill “Anton Paar MB 500” (Anton Paar GmbH, Graz, Austria) equipped with a 50 mL stainless-steel jar and a single stainless-steel grinding ball (\varnothing 25 mm). Mono- and disaccharides were extracted from the grain-based matrix by mild heating and ultrasonic treatment according to the protocol of Radenkovs et al. (2021). Samples (1.0 ± 0.1 g) were mixed with 10.0 mL of 50% acetonitrile ($H_2O:CH_3CN$, v/v), heated at $60.0^\circ C$ for 30 min, and sonicated at 50 kHz and 360 W for 30 min at $25.0 \pm 1^\circ C$ using an ultrasonic bath (J.P. Selecta®, Barcelona, Spain). The extracts were vortexed, centrifuged for 10 min at 4500 rpm ($3169 \times g$, $19.0 \pm 1^\circ C$), and filtered through a 0.22 polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) hydrophilic membrane filter (Durapore, Millipore, Billerica, MA, USA) prior to analysis. Quantitative analysis was performed using a “Waters Alliance” HPLC system (e2695) equipped with a refractive index detector (RID). Separation was achieved on an “Altima Amino” column (4.6×250 mm, $5 \mu m$) at $30.0^\circ C$ using isocratic elution with $H_2O:CH_3CN$ (20:80, v/v) at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. The injection volume was 15.0 μL . Data acquisition and processing were carried out using “Empower™ 3” software. Chromatographic separation of sugars and sugar alcohols is depicted in Fig. S3.

2.7. Determination of EP water and oil absorption capacity

For the water absorption capacity (WAC) and oil absorption capacity (OAC) tests, EPs with a moisture content of $\leq 3\%$ were weighed using an analytical balance model “Kern EMB 1200-1” (Kern & Sohn, Baden-Württemberg, Germany). The EPs were then submerged in distilled water or rapeseed oil for 30 min. After immersion, the EPs were gently blotted with a paper towel to remove any excess surface water or oil and then reweighed. The water and oil absorption capacities were calculated using the following equation (6):

$$WAC \text{ or } OAC (\%) = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_1} \times 100\% \quad (6)$$

where: W_1 – weight before absorption and W_2 – weight after absorption. The determination was performed three times ($n = 3$).

2.7.1. Water-oil penetration test

To visually evaluate the barrier performance of EPs against simultaneous oil and water exposure, a qualitative water-oil penetration test was conducted (Fig. S4). A water-oil emulsion was prepared with rhodamine dye dissolved in the aqueous phase to enable clear

visualization of liquid migration. A single drop of the dyed emulsion was placed on the surface of the EP samples and left in contact for 30 min under ambient conditions. Following exposure, the samples were manually fractured perpendicular to the surface to assess the extent of liquid penetration through the material matrix. The cross-sectional microstructure of the EPs after the penetration test was examined using a digital 3D microscope “Hirox RH-2000” (Hirox Europe, Limonest, France) equipped with a high-range triple zoom lens “MXB-5000REZ” at $35 \times$ magnification. Microscopic images were captured to observe the distribution of the rhodamine dye within the internal structure of the plates.

2.8. Microstructure analysis of EPs

The EPs were examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM), “Mira3” model, manufactured by Tescan Orsay Holding, a.s. (Brno-Kohoutovice, Czech Republic). The EPs were manually broken into small pieces (0.4×0.4 cm), mounted onto SEM pin stubs using double-sided adhesive carbon film, and coated with a 6 nm thick gold-palladium layer using a “Leica EM ACE600” vacuum sputter coater (Leica Microsystems, Wien, Austria). Non-fixed crumbs and dust particles were removed with a gentle stream of N_2 . The SEM was operated under high vacuum conditions, utilizing Secondary Electron (SE) detector. The EPs were analyzed at increasing magnifications up to $100 \times$ for precise dimension measurements, with an acceleration voltage set at 5 kV.

2.9. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

The functional groups of EP samples were analyzed using an “IR-Tracer-100” FTIR (Shimadzu Corporation, Tokyo, Japan). Approximately 1 mg of EP powder was thoroughly mixed with 100 mg of potassium bromide (KBr) and pressed into a pellet using a metal die. Spectra were recorded in the $400\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} .

2.10. Determination of 5-HMF content in EPs

To determine the 5-HMF content, 1.0 ± 0.1 g of EP matrix was mixed with 10 mL of ultra-pure water in a 50 mL conical flask and stirred for 60 min using an “ELMI MS-01” magnetic stirrer. The mixture was then transferred to 2 mL Eppendorf™ safe-lock tubes and centrifuged at 15,000 rpm for 15 min at $19 \pm 1^\circ C$ using a “Pro-Research” centrifuge (Centurion Scientific Ltd., Lancing, UK). The resulting supernatant was decanted and filtered through a $0.45 \mu m$ hydrophilic PTFE membrane before HPLC-PDA analysis. Quantitative analysis was performed on a “Shimadzu LC-20 Prominence” HPLC system (Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with an “SPD-M20A” photodiode array detector and a CTO-20AC column heater, using an “Aqueous C18” column (4.6×250 mm, $5 \mu m$; PerkinElmer). The column and detector were maintained at $25^\circ C$, with an automatic injection volume of 10 μL and loop rinsing using a 90:10 (v/v) water:acetonitrile mixture. Chromatographic separation was achieved with a mobile phase of acetonitrile and water (10:90, v/v) in gradient mode at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. Representative chromatogram of 5-HMF is depicted in Fig. S5.

2.11. Determination of tocopherol content in EPs

The tocopherols and tocotrienols were determined by the protocol of micro-saponification and HPLC-FLD (fluorescence detection) according to the previously published method (Górnaś et al., 2015).

2.12. Determination of anthocyanin content in EPs

Anthocyanins were extracted using a solvent mixture of methanol, water, and formic acid (792:198:10, $v/v/v$) via ultrasound-assisted extraction in a “Sonorex RK 510 H” ultrasonic bath (Bandelin

Electronic, Berlin, Germany), and quantified by HPLC coupled with diode array detection (HPLC-DAD), following a previously published method (Górnaś et al. (2016).

2.13. Sensory evaluation of EPs

A comprehensive sensory evaluation was conducted to assess the acceptability and sensory attributes of EPs using two complementary methods: a 5-point hedonic scale and a 12-point line scale. The 5-point hedonic scale, ranging from 1 (dislike extremely) to 5 (like extremely), was used to measure overall acceptability. Meanwhile, the 12-point line scale, ranging from 0 (dislike extremely) to 12 (like extremely), provided a more detailed assessment of specific sensory attributes: appearance, taste, firmness, and aftertaste. For the 12-point scale, the scale endpoints were anchored as 0 = “dislike extremely” and 12 = “like extremely” for all attributes. The evaluation was carried out by a trained panel of 20 individuals (14 women and 6 men), aged between 22 and 64, selected based on their sensory acuity and experience in food product evaluation. Panelists had prior experience in sensory evaluation of food products and received standardized instructions on the evaluation procedure and scale use prior to testing. For each EP, panelists were provided with two EP, i.e., one for visual inspection and one for tasting. They were instructed to break and consume pieces of the EPs to assess its properties. Appearance was evaluated as an overall visual attribute reflecting surface uniformity, presence of visible defects, and general visual appeal. All EPs were anonymized using random codes to avoid bias, and samples were presented in randomized order. Water was provided for mouth rinsing between samples to minimize flavor carry-over and improve rating accuracy. All evaluations were conducted under controlled conditions at room temperature (22 ± 2 °C). Data from both scales were analyzed to determine consumer preferences and identify areas for improvement in the formulation and sensory quality of the EPs.

Because the panelists were trained and experienced in food evaluation and no personal or sensitive data were collected, institutional ethical approval was not required. All participants provided informed consent prior to participation, and the study procedures respected

participant rights and privacy.

2.14. Statistical analysis

All data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) from at least three independent replicates. Statistical analyses were performed using “IBM SPSS Statistics” for Windows, version 25 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). To assess differences between EPs, a one-way ANOVA was conducted using the General Linear Model (UNIVARIATE). Post hoc pairwise comparisons were based on estimated marginal means with Tukey’s HSD test applied to control for Type I error. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was used. Different lowercase superscripts (a–k) in tables and figures indicate significant differences between EPs. Additionally, a heatmap was generated to visualize the distribution and relationships among sensory and nutritional variables (Table S1), using “XLSTAT 2025” (Addinsoft Inc., New York, NY, USA) integrated with “Microsoft Excel 2019” (Microsoft Corp., Redmond, WA, USA). Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was also performed using “SPSS Statistics” to further assess the underlying patterns and associations among the variables.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Visual and color characteristics of EPs

EP color ranged from light brown (EPs 1.2 and 12.1) to dark brown with purplish undertones (EPs 25.1, 21.2, 15.1) (Fig. 1). Color differences were primarily due to the share of BP. EPs with higher BP (10%) (EPs 25.1, 15.1) and apple puree (10%) (EPs 28.1, 7.2) exhibited darker coloration. In contrast, EPs with moderate BP content (4–5%) and higher WB (70–90%) shares (EPs 1.2 and 12.1) displayed more uniform color and overall structural integrity. Visible signs of bubbling, caused by extensive water evaporation during molding, were observed in EP 25.1, the only EP containing 1.2% potato starch. The uneven color and texture highlight the challenges of optimizing thermal molding conditions and the used ingredients in the formulations. To quantitatively support these observations Table 2 presents the CIELAB color coordinates (L^* , a^* , b^*),

Fig. 1. Digital photographs of EPs prepared with varying formulations according to Table 1. (A) 18.2, (B) 28.1, (C) 7.2, (D) 25.1, (E) 21.2, (F) 15.1, (G) 16.1, (H) 1.2, (I) 12.1, (J) 14.1, (K) 22.2. **Note:** The visual characteristics of the EPs were established using a Xiaomi Redmi 13 (model 24040RN64Y, Xiaomi Corporation, Beijing, China) smartphone, equipped with a 108 MP primary camera. Photos were captured under controlled lighting conditions using a white background to ensure uniformity and minimize external visual noise.

Table 2
Colorimetric parameters (L^* , a^* , b^* , ΔE , chroma, browning index, and hue angle) of EPs.

EP	L^*	a^*	b^*	ΔE (from 1.2)	Chroma (C^*)	Browning index (BI)	h°
18.2	40.91 ± 4.74 ^c	10.00 ± 0.24 ^f	23.08 ± 1.04 ^c	8.02 ± 0.19	25.07 ± 1.13 ^d	97.64 ± 1.24 ^g	66.57 ± 1.14 ^b
28.1	27.94 ± 3.68 ^j	10.86 ± 0.71 ^c	24.7 ± 2.42 ^b	21.11 ± 0.24	26.91 ± 1.98 ^b	190.85 ± 2.13 ^b	66.27 ± 2.19 ^b
7.2	31.63 ± 3.76 ^h	10.04 ± 0.64 ^f	24.28 ± 1.89 ^b	17.37 ± 0.32	26.23 ± 1.79 ^c	150.80 ± 2.43 ^d	67.53 ± 3.98 ^a
25.1	35.64 ± 4.28 ^g	11.53 ± 0.50 ^a	13.53 ± 1.45 ^g	15.53 ± 0.32	17.92 ± 0.24 ^f	70.43 ± 1.19 ^j	49.56 ± 2.97 ^d
21.2	27.81 ± 10.79 ^k	10.69 ± 0.80 ^d	24.79 ± 2.44 ^b	21.24 ± 0.89	26.87 ± 2.16 ^b	193.05 ± 3.14 ^a	66.67 ± 3.11 ^b
15.1	38.55 ± 6.58 ^e	11.40 ± 0.70 ^b	14.01 ± 1.38 ^f	12.85 ± 0.12	18.06 ± 0.78 ^f	65.96 ± 2.97 ^k	50.50 ± 4.67 ^b
16.1	29.71 ± 8.24 ⁱ	10.35 ± 0.63 ^e	22.61 ± 1.96 ^d	19.12 ± 0.78	24.89 ± 1.56 ^d	151.15 ± 2.14 ^c	65.40 ± 3.87 ^c
1.2	48.79 ± 3.35 ^a	9.77 ± 0.59 ^g	21.60 ± 1.02 ^e	0	23.66 ± 0.86 ^e	71.91 ± 1.98 ⁱ	65.66 ± 3.23 ^c
12.1	39.12 ± 7.15 ^d	9.27 ± 0.59 ^b	21.62 ± 1.30 ^e	9.68 ± 0.05	23.54 ± 0.78 ^e	94.79 ± 2.17 ^h	66.79 ± 4.03 ^b
14.1	41.63 ± 11.85 ^b	10.35 ± 2.65 ^e	24.30 ± 6.25 ^b	7.67 ± 0.05	26.29 ± 3.14 ^c	101.93 ± 1.65 ^f	66.93 ± 3.76 ^a
22.2	36.12 ± 7.89 ^f	10.72 ± 0.54 ^d	25.27 ± 2.34 ^a	13.22 ± 0.12	27.34 ± 1.78 ^a	131.63 ± 3.01 ^e	67.01 ± 3.43 ^a

Note: Values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation ($n = 15$) for L^* , a^* , and b^* values. Values with different lowercase superscript letters differ significantly ($p < 0.05$). EP 1.2 in color analysis was used as reference EP due to relatively higher L^* value. EP – edible plate.

total color difference (ΔE), chroma (C^*), browning index (BI), and hue angle (h°) for EPs made with different WB and BP formulations using molding. Lightness (L^*) ranged from 27.81 (21.2) to 48.79 (reference EP 1.2), the latter formulated with 90% WB, 4% BP, and 3% apple puree. EPs 21.2 and 28.1 had the lowest L^* values (27.81 and 27.94, respectively), indicating darker coloration. This is due to higher sugar content from apple puree, lactose, and sugar syrup, facilitating non-enzymatic browning mechanisms, including Maillard reactions and caramelization, during thermal molding (Lund and Ray, 2017). The red-green coordinate (a^*) ranged from 9.27 (EP 12.1) to 11.53 (EP 25.1), with intense red tones linked to anthocyanin-rich BP. Organic acids like citric and lactic acids likely stabilized anthocyanins, enhancing color retention during heating (Kowalski and Gonzalez de Mejia, 2021; Lv et al., 2022). The yellow-blue axis (b^*) showed wider variation (13.53 to 25.27), with EP 25.1 having the strongest blue hue and 22.2 the most yellow. Higher b^* values were again linked to BP presence. Total color difference (ΔE) relative to the reference EP was highest in EP 21.2

(21.25), while 14.1 and 18.2 showed minimal variation, indicating close visual resemblance to the baseline. Chroma (C^*) values, reflecting color saturation, ranged from 17.92 to 27.34. EPs with more apple puree and syrup showed greater C^* values due to intensified Maillard and caramelization reactions and the presence of natural pigments. The browning index (BI), an indicator of non-enzymatic browning (Gómez-Narváez et al., 2019), ranged from 70.43 (25.1) to 193.05 (21.2). High BI in darker EPs is associated with the Maillard reactions and caramelization, which promote melanoidin formation, intensifying browning and reducing lightness (Sharma et al., 2021). Hue angle (h°) mostly ranged from 65 to 67°, indicating yellowish-red tones (McGuire, 2019). EPs 25.1 and 15.1 showed lower hue angles (~50°), suggesting a redder appearance due to increased a^* and reduced b^* values, consistent with higher BP.

Fig. 2. Physical and mechanical properties of EPs. **A** – Individual thickness measurements of EPs (mm), where green bars indicate measurements taken at the edge (1), gray bars at the plate rise (2, slope), and orange bars near the center (3, flat base); **B** – Fracture force (N); **C** – Water absorption capacity (%); **D** – Oil absorption capacity (%). Values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation ($n = 3$). Values with different lowercase superscript letters differ significantly ($p < 0.05$). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

3.2. Thickness evaluation of EPs

The thickness of the EPs varied within the different formulations, showing differences in ingredient composition and behavior under the applied molding conditions (Fig. 2A). The flat base generally exhibited the highest thickness values among all EPs, sometimes exceeding 4.0 mm. EP 12.1 reached a maximum of 5.11 mm, while EP 16.1 showed a minimum value of 3.16 mm. The slope region consistently displayed lower thicknesses, typically around 2.7–3.3 mm, with maximum value observed in EP 12.1 and minimum in EPs 16.1, 22.2, and 18.2. The EP thickness difference can be associated with material flow and redistribution during pressing as a function of EP composition.

Meanwhile, the edges showed moderate thickness, usually between 3.0 and 3.5 mm. Again, the highest value was observed in EP 12.1 and the lowest in EP 16.1. This suggests that the EP 12.1 may demonstrate stronger performance in terms of resistance to fracture force. This gradation in thickness increasing from slope to base is characteristic of thermoforming or pressure molding processes, where material compression and flow are uneven due to mold geometry and applied force distribution (Erdogan and Eksi, 2014).

3.3. Fracture force analysis of EPs

The fracture force, indicating the mechanical strength of the EPs under stress, varied significantly within different formulations (Fig. 2B), with values ranging from 30.0 N in EP 14.1 to 235.2 N in EP 16.1. The results showed no correlation between EP thickness and fracture resistance. Notably, EP 16.1, despite being thinner, exhibited the highest fracture force. This EP contained gluten, 5% lactic acid, and other structuring agents, which contributed to its dense matrix. Lactic acid is a complexing agent that reduces porosity and strengthens the structure (Dülger et al., 2024). On the other hand, EP 14.1, lacking lactic acid and with minimal gluten and excess moisture from apple puree, showed the lowest fracture strength (30.0 N), reflecting a more flexible, weaker network. However, the observed value is still higher than that reported by Andrejko & Blicharz-Kania (2024) for flaxseed-based tableware. EPs with higher gluten content (e.g., 18.2, 16.1, 21.2) exhibited higher fracture forces, highlighting the role of gluten in enhancing cohesion and matrix stability (Vinod et al., 2023). Conversely, EPs with lower gluten content and lactic acid (e.g. 1.2 and 7.2), displayed significantly lower fracture forces due to reduced structural binders. In comparison, the higher pectin content from apple puree likely contributed to a more flexible, less rigid matrix. This is consistent with findings from Asfaw et al. (2023) on the effect of pectin on edible films. Additionally, EPs 15.1 and 28.1, which lacked glycerol and contained more BP, showed decreased strength due to weaker matrix formation and the absence of plasticizing effect attributed to glycerol. Balancing plasticizers (e.g., glycerol, lactic acid) and structural binders (e.g., gluten, xanthan) is crucial to optimizing mechanical properties for EPs.

3.4. Water and oil absorption capacity of EPs

WAC is a crucial property of edible packaging, affecting structural integrity and suitability to humid environments (Herrera-Vazquez et al., 2022). WAC values varied from 16.14% (EP 16.1) to 64.62% (EP 1.2), reflecting significant variations in composition and structure (Fig. 2C). EP 1.2, with the highest WAC (64.62%), contained 90% of WB, glycerol, and apple puree, ingredients with high water-binding capacity (Salinas et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2024). Its lack of structural agents such as gluten or xanthan resulted in a less compact, more heterogeneous matrix with delamination and void-like regions, which facilitated water uptake. In contrast, EP 16.1 showed the lowest WAC (16.14%) due to the inclusion of gluten, which contributed to forming a cohesive protein network that limited water penetration (Kunanopparat et al., 2008). The absence of fruit-derived low-molecular weight sugars and organic acids may have further stabilized the matrix under humid conditions due to

reduced hygroscopicity (Jaya and Das, 2009). EP 21.2 also had low WAC (27.95%) despite a lower share of WB (67%) due to the presence of xanthan gum (5%), which improves water resistance by forming a dense matrix (Hernández-García et al., 2021). Xanthan also appeared to counteract the hygroscopic nature of glycerol and sugar syrup. EPs 15.1 and 12.1 also showed high WAC, corresponding to 49.93% and 49.02%, due to apple puree and glycerol, but lacked xanthan, resulting in higher permeability. Intermediate values were observed in EPs 25.1, 22.2, and 7.2, which were formulated with variable content of gluten, lactic acid, and fruit-based ingredients. Their moderate WAC values suggest a balanced interplay between water-retaining and matrix-stabilizing components. EP 14.1 was excluded from the analysis due to structural failure during testing. Notably, EPs 28.1, 7.2, 15.1, 1.2, 12.1 showed pronounced swelling and visible signs of fiber separation when exposed to moisture, indicating poor water resistance and unsuitability for use in contact with liquids. This behavior is consistent with the SEM observations, as formulations with higher puree content and/or higher BP tended to exhibit a looser, less compact and more heterogeneous microstructure, with delamination and void-like regions that facilitate water uptake and swelling.

OAC indicates a material's ability to interact with hydrophobic compounds. It is relevant for flavor retention and mechanical flexibility in edible packaging (Rishi et al., 2024). OAC values among the EPs ranged from 1.80% (16.1) to 8.73% (14.1), reflecting differences in composition and surface characteristics (Fig. 2D). EP 14.1 showed the highest OAC value (8.73%), likely due to its high apple puree content (12.88%), moderate gluten, and absence of xanthan gum, factors contributing to greater heterogeneous microstructure and surface roughness. Dextran and levan may have contributed to an open matrix structure facilitating oil penetration (Domżał-Kędzia et al., 2023). In contrast, EP 16.1 had the lowest OAC value (1.80%), with a dense, gluten-rich matrix and no fruit-derived sugars, limiting oil interaction, consistent with findings revealing that compact protein networks reduce lipid uptake (Rhim and Ng, 2007). Intermediate OAC were observed in EPs 1.2 (5.36%), 22.2 (5.30%), and 25.1 (4.22%), likely due to formulation-driven differences in matrix compactness and surface properties arising from fiber, polyols, gluten, and fruit puree. EP 15.1 also showed higher OAC (6.75%), which may be influenced by changes in microstructure and surface chemistry associated with lactic acid and BP components (Alba et al., 2018). Acid-induced hydrolysis may have further loosened the structure, enhancing oil absorption. Low OAC values (2.02–2.06%) were recorded in EPs 18.2, 7.2, and 16.1, where minimal plasticizers and acid additives resulted in compact, bran-dominant matrices with limited oil-binding capacity.

3.5. Water-oil penetration behavior of EPs

The water-oil penetration test provided a clear and intuitive illustration of the behavior of the EPs when exposed to moisture and grease. In all EP formulations, the rhodamine-dyed emulsion remained mainly at the surface, forming a thin colored layer and showing no deep penetration into the internal structure (Fig. S4). Given the average EP thickness of approximately 4 mm (flat base), the maximum observed penetration corresponded to about 2.5% of the total thickness, indicating that liquid migration was largely confined to the surface layer. Overall, the EP matrices effectively resisted simultaneous water and oil penetration, even after prolonged contact. Although minor surface irregularities were observed in some formulations, these did not result in significant liquid migration through the material. In contrast, the paper control exhibited rapid and uniform dye penetration throughout the material, reaching approximately 20.4% of its thickness, which was several times higher than that observed for the developed EPs. This behavior reflects the porous and highly hydrophilic nature of paper-based materials. Overall, the results of this qualitative penetration experiment reinforce the strong barrier performance of the EPs and are consistent with the quantitative water and oil absorption results. Future

work will therefore focus on systematic comparative assessments between EPs, paper-based disposables, and commercial biodegradable plastics under harmonized testing frameworks.

3.6. Microstructural characterization of EPs by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM analysis revealed pronounced differences in the surface morphology and internal architecture of EPs, directly attributable to their compositional variations (Fig. 3). EPs with high WB content (70–90%) combined with cohesive additives, such as gluten, lecithin, or xanthan gum, including 15.1, 16.1, 18.2, and 21.2 exhibited compact, layered cross-sections with tightly packed fibers and minimal void spaces. Their surfaces appeared continuous and relatively smooth, particularly in EPs 16.1 and 21.2, where structural integrity was further supported by an undamaged outer pericarp and brush-like hairs, indicating effective compaction during pressing. Xanthan gum, included in EPs 21.2 and 28.1, enhanced matrix viscosity and contributed to the stabilization of fiber distribution during processing, thereby reducing structural collapse and delamination. These observations are consistent with previous studies reporting that hydrocolloids such as xanthan gum enhance structural integrity by increasing matrix viscosity, improving phase homogeneity, and limiting collapse or delamination during

thermal and mechanical processing (Tabassum et al., 2025). These EPs exhibited fewer surface fissures and more coherent internal lamellae, highlighting the role of xanthan gum as a rheological modifier and physical stabilizer. In contrast, EPs, including 1.2, 7.2, 12.1, with higher content of plasticizers, e.g., glycerol and apple puree (rich in sugars and sugar alcohols, particularly sorbitol), and reduced or absent structural binders exhibited disrupted, flaky-like surface textures and highly heterogeneous, delaminated cross-sectional interiors. These matrices revealed loose fiber packing, void spaces, and interlayer separation, indicating weaker cohesion and impaired mechanical stability. Intermediate structures were observed in EPs such as 14.1, 25.1, 28.1, and 22.2, where the incorporation of additives such as BP, chitosan, or organic acids contributed to heterogeneous yet moderately compacted morphologies, consistent with previous reports on composite biopolymer systems (Souza et al., 2020). In these cases, micro-cracks, uneven fiber distribution, and delamination with void-like discontinuities reflected partial compatibility between matrix components. Notably, formulations containing higher BP levels ($\geq 8\text{--}10\%$) and/or 10% apple puree more frequently exhibited heterogeneous cross-sections with void-like regions, delamination, and structural defects, whereas moderate BP inclusion (4–5%) combined with structurally supportive additives, such as gluten or xanthan resulted in denser and more coherent architectures. This structural variability was

Fig. 3. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrographs of EPs according to Table 1.

reflected in functional performance. Compact microstructures were associated with high fracture force (Fig. 2) in the range of approximately 150 to 235 N and low WAC of about 16 to 28%, whereas visibly void spaces and delaminated morphologies corresponded to low fracture force of roughly 30 to 70 N and high WAC of about 49 to 65%. SEM observations indicated that the interaction between fiber sources and functional additives substantially influences the physical architecture of the formed EPs, which in turn affects their durability, barrier properties, and overall suitability for practical applications.

3.7. FTIR analysis, the content of sugars, 5-HMF and sugar alcohol, and PCA evaluation

FTIR analysis revealed key molecular changes in the EPs following

thermal processing at 160 °C (Fig. 4A and B). Since WB fibers and other polysaccharide-containing additives are the predominant components of the EP composition, the spectra of the samples are superficially similar to that of cellulose (Yazdanbakhsh and Rashidi, 2020). Broad O–H stretching bands at 3200–3400 cm^{-1} assigned to hydrogen bonding, enhanced by interactions among hydroxyl-rich biopolymers and thermal moisture redistribution (Zhang et al., 2024). Aliphatic C–H stretching between 2857 and 2928 cm^{-1} reflected lipid and carbohydrate contributions (Cremer and Kaletunç, 2003) and also indicated the formation of aliphatic degradation products or crosslinked structures arising from thermal decomposition of sugars and Maillard-type reactions (Surendra and Veerabhadraswamy, 2017). In protein-rich formulations, such as EP 7.2 or 15.1 (Table S1), the presence of amide I (near 1650 cm^{-1}) and amide II (near 1540 cm^{-1}) bands suggests protein denaturation and

Fig. 4. FTIR spectral profiling (A–B), the content of 5-HMF and total sugars (C), and their multivariate relationships using PCA (D). **Note:** Values are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation ($n = 3$) (5-HMF mg/100 g, Total sugar g/100 g, dry weight basis). Values with different lowercase superscript letters differ significantly ($p < 0.05$). Glycerol was excluded from the total sugar calculation due to its non-involvement as a direct precursor in the Maillard reaction. The PCA plot includes variables related to formulation composition, mechanical properties, color, and phytochemical content. Carbohydrate-related variables include fructose, glucose, and sucrose, which are common sugars in the EPs, as well as “TotalSugar,” representing their cumulative content. “Sugarsyrupad” refers to sugar syrup added to the formulation, while “Glycerol” and “Glycerolad” indicate the presence and addition of glycerol as a plasticizer. “Lactad” represents lactose added to the formulation. “HMF” denotes 5-hydroxymethylfurfural, a thermal degradation product of sugars. Acid-related variables include “LAad” (lactic acid added), while “WA” and “OA” represent water and oil absorption, respectively. Color measurements include “L*” (lightness), “a*” (red-green axis), and “b*” (yellow-blue axis), along with “Croma” (color saturation) and “BI” (browning index). Mechanical properties are represented by “Fracture” (fracture force). “AP,” “WB,” and “BP” refer to apple puree, wheat bran, and blackcurrant pomace, respectively. Phytochemical variables include “TotalAnth” (total anthocyanins), “C3G” (cyanidin-3-glucoside), “C3R” (cyanidin-3-rutinoside), “D3G” (delphinidin-3-glucoside), and “D3R” (delphinidin-3-rutinoside), as well as unidentified anthocyanin peaks labeled “AU1,” “AU2,” and “AU3.” Tocopherol-related variables include “TotalT” (total tocopherols) and the individual homologues “alfaT,” “betaT,” “gammaT,” and “deltaT.” Tocotrienol-related compounds are listed as “TotalT3,” “alfaT3,” and “betaT3.” EP identifiers such as “12.1,” “28.1,” and others represent specific formulation variants analyzed in the study. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Maillard-type crosslinking, likely induced by the thermal load applied during press-formation of the product (Akilhoğlu et al., 2022; Baldassarre et al., 2012; Poulsen et al., 2013). Absorptions at 1660–1675 cm^{-1} and 900–1020 cm^{-1} , particularly intense in sugar-rich samples such as EPs 7.2, 21.2, 22.2, and 25.1, correspond to C=O stretching and furan ring vibrations of 5-HMF, a known marker of caramelization and Maillard reactions (Mengstie and Habtu, 2020). The region between 990 and 1060 cm^{-1} arises from overlapping vibrational bands attributed to C–O–C, C–C, C–O, and C–CH groups (Gieroba et al., 2023), further supporting the presence of polysaccharide-derived thermal degradation products. Additionally, a distinct C=O absorption at 1744 cm^{-1} , detected in multiple samples, may correspond to aldehyde or ester functionalities, further evidencing Maillard-derived compounds (Lievens et al., 2011). Signals around 1400–1450 cm^{-1} suggest C–H bending and carboxylate presence (Enders et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2025), while strong bands at 1000–1150 cm^{-1} , especially in EPs 7.2 and 25.1, reflect C–O and C–C stretching of polysaccharides, implying partial rearrangement or degradation (Hong et al., 2021).

Complementary HPLC analysis confirmed the presence of 5-HMF as a heat-induced Maillard reaction product, with concentrations ranging from 0.76 to 37.19 mg/100 g DW (Fig. 4C). EPs 21.2, 22.2, and 25.1 showed the highest concentrations, consistent with FTIR data that confirming the presence of aldehyde and carbonyl absorption bands. This increase in 5-HMF was associated with the presence of reducing sugars, thermolabile ingredients (e.g., sugar syrup), and acidulants such as citric acid and NaCl, which may catalyze sugar dehydration under mildly acidic conditions (Kammoun et al., 2019; Sajid et al., 2020). In particular, apple-puree-derived sugars provide reactive carbonyl precursors, while citric and lactic acids lower pH and accelerate sugar dehydration reactions, jointly promoting 5-HMF formation during press-molding at elevated temperature. From a health perspective, 5-HMF has attracted attention due to reports of cytotoxic and genotoxic effects at high exposure levels; however, its occurrence is common in thermally processed foods (Capuano and Fogliano, 2011). Although 5-HMF is not currently regulated in edible packaging materials, reference limits established for food products provide a useful benchmark. For example, European legislation restricts 5-HMF levels in honey to 4 mg/100 g (8 mg/100 g for tropical honeys) (Council Directive 2001/110/EC of 20 December 2001 relating to honey, 2002), whereas substantially higher concentrations are routinely reported in widely consumed foods such as breakfast cereals, baked goods, and roasted coffee, where values between 24 and 120 mg/100 g have been documented (Choudhary et al., 2021; Martins et al., 2022). In this context, the maximum concentration observed in the present study (37.19 mg/100 g DW) falls within the range reported for common heat-processed foods. Nevertheless, given the edible nature of the plates and their intended contact with food, minimizing 5-HMF formation remains desirable, and adherence to the “as low as reasonably achievable” (ALARA) principle is recommended (Shapla et al., 2018). Several formulation and processing strategies can be applied to mitigate 5-HMF formation in EPs. These include optimization of thermal processing conditions, particularly lowering heating temperatures and reducing residence times, which directly influence Maillard reaction kinetics (Choudhary et al., 2021). In addition, reducing the content of free reducing sugars and thermolabile sweeteners, as well as careful control of formulation acidity, may significantly limit sugar dehydration pathways leading to 5-HMF formation (Pantović et al., 2025). The selection and dosage of acidulants should therefore be balanced to achieve functional performance without promoting excessive thermal degradation. Furthermore, the incorporation of antioxidant-rich ingredients, such as blackcurrant pomace, may partially suppress oxidative and carbonyl-driven reaction pathways, although this effect is formulation-dependent (Abrantes et al., 2022; Hu et al., 2022). Overall, rational formulation design combined with controlled processing conditions represents an effective strategy to limit 5-HMF formation while preserving the mechanical, sensory, and functional properties of EPs.

The sugar composition of EPs, detailed in Table S2, varied significantly by formulation. Glycerol, used as a plasticizer, was the predominant sugar alcohol (0.69–9.66 g/100 g DW). Sucrose ranged from 1.19 to 2.99 g/100 g DW and was primarily influenced by apple puree and sugar syrup. Glucose and fructose levels were modest, while lactose was detected only in dairy-based EPs. Arabinose content remained relatively stable due to its presence in WB and BP. PCA integrated data on 5-HMF, sugar composition, and formulation variables (Fig. 4D). EPs with high BP or syrup clustered distinctly due to increased 5-HMF and total sugars, while WB-rich, sugar-minimal EPs grouped separately, reflecting their lower reactivity.

3.8. The content of bioactive compounds in EPs

3.8.1. The content of tocopherols

Among the eight tested tocopherols, four tocopherols (T) and four tocotrienols (T3), all EPs showed the highest concentration of β -T3, followed by α -T, γ -T, β -T, α -T3, and δ -T (Table S3). The total content of T3 and T ranged from 2.73 to 3.49 mg/100 g DW and 2.27 to 4.71 mg/100 g DW, respectively, depending on the composition of the plant-based materials used in the EP formulations (Fig. 5A). These results are consistent with findings from cereal-based matrices, where β -T3, although the rarest T3 homologue in nature, has been reported as the predominant tocopherol in wheat, spelt, and barley bran fractions (Górnaś et al., 2015; Lachman et al., 2018). In contrast, α - and γ -T primarily originated from BP, a well-documented source of these tocopherols (Górnaś et al., 2016). Notably, the concentration of β -T3 in the EPs was, on average, 50% lower than the mean content reported in WB of various origins (Górnaś et al., 2015), suggesting its losses during thermal processing. This is in line with previous studies showing that the recovery of tocopherols and tocotrienols after muffin baking was below 50% (Mildner-Szkudlarz et al., 2016). Additionally, alkylresorcinols, recognized markers of whole-grain products (Martín-García et al., 2021), were detected during tocopherol identification; however, due to the lack of available standards, quantification was not performed.

3.8.2. The content of anthocyanins

All tested EPs were dominated by four anthocyanins characteristic of blackcurrant: delphinidin-3-O-glucoside, delphinidin-3-O-rutinoside, cyanidin-3-O-glucoside, and cyanidin-3-O-rutinoside (Table S4) (Górnaś et al., 2016). In addition to these major compounds, three minor anthocyanins were also detected; however, their structures could not be identified due to the absence of appropriate analytical standards. The total anthocyanin content ranged from 58.22 to 195.38 mg/100 g DW, depending on the proportion of BP incorporated into the EP formulations (Fig. 5B). It is well established that thermal processing, such as baking, particularly in products enriched with anthocyanin-rich by-products, leads to significant degradation of thermolabile anthocyanins, with reported losses often exceeding 50% (Górnaś et al., 2016; Mildner-Szkudlarz et al., 2016). In the present study, the limited number of tested concentrations and formulations does not allow for conclusive assessment of the potential influence of additive type on anthocyanin stability during EP production.

3.9. Sensory evaluation of EPs

According to data from a sensory evaluation using a 5-point hedonic scale, the EPs generally received modest consumer acceptance (Fig. 6A). Most scores fell below the neutral “like” value of 3.0, with substantial variation depending on ingredient composition. EP 25.1 achieved the highest mean score of 3.07, indicating a generally favorable impression and suggesting it was the only EP that panelists clearly liked. EPs 18.1 and 28.1 received scores of 2.93, indicating a moderate level of acceptance, while EP 22.2 was close behind with a score of 2.87. Conversely, the EPs with the lowest ratings, 1.2 (1.87) and 15.1 (1.93), were disliked, emphasizing notable shortcomings in their sensory

Fig. 5. The content of bioactive compounds in EPs. **A** – Total tocopherol and tocotrienol content; **B** – total anthocyanin content. **Note:** Values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation ($n = 3$) (mg/100 g, dry weight basis). Values with different lowercase superscript letters differ significantly ($p < 0.05$).

Fig. 6. Sensory evaluation scores based on a 5-point hedonic scale (A) and 12-point line scale (B) evaluation and nutritional profile of EPs (C).

characteristics. Other EPs, including 7.1, 16.1, 12.1, and 14.1, received intermediate scores ranging from 2.27 to 2.47, implying a trend towards disfavor or neutrality. In summary, the findings suggest that although certain EPs, particularly EP 25.1, exhibit potential, enhancements in formulation are essential to improve consumer preference and attain

wider acceptance.

According to data from a sensory evaluation using a 12-point line scale, the sensory quality of EPs varied significantly depending on ingredient composition and formulation strategy (Fig. 6B). Among the evaluated attributes, appearance, taste, firmness, and aftertaste, the

results highlight that the most favorable sensory profiles were achieved by carefully balancing functional ingredients, particularly moisture retainers, sweeteners, and acidulants. EP 25.1 received the highest overall appearance score (8.71), with a strong performance in taste (6.57) and firmness (6.86), suggesting a visually appealing and structurally balanced product. Its formulation included 70% WB, 10% BP, apple puree, glycerol, gluten, sugar syrup, lecithin, and organic acids (citric and lactic), contributing to desirable color, texture, and taste. Nutritionally (g/100 g), it was moderate in protein (11.83), and rich in fiber (35.2) and fat (5.99), making it both sensorially and nutritionally balanced (Fig. 6C). EP 21.2, evaluated highest in taste (7.05), also displayed sufficient appearance and firmness, revealing the role of a blend of sugar syrup, citric acid, and glycerol. These not only enhanced palatability but also helped balance grainy flavor profile typically associated with bran. Its nutritional profile showed the highest carbohydrate content (66.87 g) and significant fiber (36.2 g), making it an energy-rich but still fiber-dense option. In contrast, EP 1.2 was the lowest rated in taste (3.60) and firmness (4.85), despite high nutritional value, especially fiber (40.6 g) and protein (15.81 g). It lacked sweeteners, acidulants, and emulsifiers, leading to a dry, grainy mouthfeel and poor texture. This exemplifies the limitation of bran-dominant formulations (90% WB) without sufficient functional additives. Similarly, EP 15.1 and 16.1, both composed of 80% WB and devoid of flavor-enhancing or structural agents, scored poorly in taste and aftertaste. Despite their high protein (>16 g) and fiber (>36 g) content, these EPs exhibited taste and aftertaste drawbacks typical of overly bran-rich, unbalanced formulations, revealing the importance of incorporating sensory-enhancing components such as fat. This is further supported by EP 28.1, which had a high-fat content (13.37 g) due to 10% lecithin and moderate apple puree, which contributed to a softer mouthfeel and acceptable taste (5.81) and appearance (7.50). However, its aftertaste score was low (4.19), possibly due to a persistent fatty sensation not sufficiently balanced by acidulants. EP 22.2 has been distinguished by its firmness, achieving 8.19 points, reflecting remarkable structural integrity. This EP comprised 75% WB, 5% BP, and xanthan gum, a recognized texturizer that likely improved its crispness. With the highest carbohydrate content of 67.51 g and substantial fiber content of 38.1 g, it provides both structural and nutritional benefits. The results indicate that although the high dietary fiber and protein levels in WB-based EPs are nutritional advantages, they do not guarantee sensory appeal. Adding glycerol, sugar syrup, apple puree, lecithin, xanthan gum, and mild acidulants is crucial for improving flavor, texture, and overall acceptability by consumers. Considering the physicochemical characteristics, EP 21.2 effectively demonstrates a balance of firmness, nutritional value, and sensory attributes, making it a strong candidate for further research with potential applications.

4. Conclusion

The present study demonstrated the potential of re-purposing food processing by-products into EPs through a zero-waste approach, offering functional, environmental, and potential health benefits. The results showed that the choice of ingredients and additives significantly influenced the physicochemical properties, consumer acceptance, and the content of health-promoting compounds such as anthocyanins, tocopherols, and tocotrienols, as well as the formation of undesirable substances like 5-HMF. Future research should aim to optimize formulations with a focus on health and safety, including strategies to reduce thermal degradation products and mitigate allergen risks, such as the presence of gluten and lactose. For practical applications, the production of smaller and thinner vessels is recommended to facilitate their complete consumption together with food. From both microbiological and functional perspectives, EPs appear better suited as components of larger serving systems, such as inserts for sauces, side dishes, or small salads, rather than as primary containers for full meals.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Vitalijs Radenkovs: Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Karina Juhnevcica-Radenkova:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Paweł Górnaś:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Dmitrijs Jakovlevs:** Visualization, Software, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Martins Andzs:** Methodology, Investigation. **Inta Krasnova:** Investigation. **Daniels Udalovs:** Investigation. **Ingmars Cinkmanis:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Jorens Kviesis:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Anda Valdovska:** Resources, Formal analysis. **Dalija Seglina:** Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2026.147817>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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